

PEDAGOGICAL ESP APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FORMATION OF A CULTURE OF INNOVATION IN THE TRAINING OF OIL AND GAS SPECIALISTS

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Abstract. *The purpose of this manuscript was to familiarize the pedagogical community with modern trends and ways to improve the efficiency of the educational process of training specialists of oil and gas industry, to analyze the main problems using modern pedagogical technologies and methodological approaches, to assess the main areas of training that meet the modern requirements of the organization of the educational process.*

Keywords: *educational process, ESP teaching, pedagogical methods, qualification, innovation, interactive, oil and gas industry.*

Organization of the educational process, at the current stage of the development of higher education, demanding special, increased requirements on the teaching staff of universities. They must have high professional knowledge, confidently poses modern forms and methods of educational work, constantly improve pedagogical and professional qualifications. This, in turn requires the teaching staff of the higher education to constantly improve, work on themselves, increase both moral and spiritual and intellectual potential.

Humanity has entered a new phase of the informational revolution. Therefore, the level of training of a modern specialist, in addition to professional knowledge of the basic of specialty general technical, social and humanitarian sciences is largely determined by this following capabilities:

Inclusion in the global information space; the ability to effectively organize and maintain professional and random information processes; the ability competently operate information resources (accumulate, save, apply) and use appropriate range of technical means for this; the ability to work effectively with information (to find transform present formalize in a form convenient for further use and transmission, etc.).

Thus, one of the important requirements for improving the efficiency of the educational process at the university is increasing the intellectual level of the teacher, his scientific potential and practical experience. And, it should be added here that increasing intellectual level is a constant process and directly depends on the research activity of the teacher. The next main requirement for improving the effectiveness of the educational process is the constant improvement of the methodical culture and pedagogical skills of the teacher.

Currently, the concept of pedagogical technology has firmly entered the pedagogical lexicon. Today there are more than a hundred educational technologies. The main disadvantage of the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process is a low innovative qualification of a teacher, especially the ability to choose a necessary technology, methodology, an oriented book, as well as the organization and construction of a pilot installation, conducting an implementation experiment, skills for diagnosing the dynamics of experiments. Current my research in ESP teaching for oil and gas students shows that a comparative methods and

appropriate illustration providing the visual aids would be the effective ways in terms of progress in learning English for careers, in my case oil and gas industry. In order to practice and being sure how its work I created the handle book as a dictionary for each units of the main text book from a based curricular.

Below here some fragments of the book which I mentioned earlier.

Some teachers are not ready to innovate methodically, others psychologically, and others technologically. Here it is appropriate to recall ESP methods of teaching. The passive method in ESP teaching is a form of interaction between students and the teacher, in which the teacher is the main actor and the manager of the course of the lesson, and the trainees act as passive listener. The teacher's communication with students in passive classes is carried out through surveys, independent, control works, tests, etc. From the standpoint of pedagogical technologies and the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition, the passive method is considered the most ineffective, but despite this, it has some advantages. This is a relatively easy to prepare for the lesson by the teacher and the opportunity to present a significant amount educational material in a limited time frame of the lesson. A lecture is the most common type of passive activity. The active method in ESP teaching is a form of interaction between the trainees and the teacher, in which the teacher and the trainees interact with each other during the lesson and the trainees are active participants in the lesson. If passive methods assumed an authoritarian style of interaction, then active methods assume a democratic style more. There is similarity between active and interactive methods, but they have differences. Interactive methods can be considered as the most modern form active methods. Interactive method means to interact, to be in a conversation mode, a dialogue with someone. Unlike active methods, interactive methods are focused on a broader interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other and on the dominance of the activity of students in the course of the lesson. The teacher's place in interactive classes is reduced the direction of the trainees' activities to achieve the objectives of the lesson. The teacher also develops a lesson plan, usually these are interactive exercises and tasks, during which the student studies the material. Therefore, the main components of interactive classes are interactive exercises and

tasks that are performed by trainees. An important difference between interactive exercises and tasks from the usual ones is that by performing them, students not only consolidate the already studied material, but also study a new one. Thus, by interactive learning, the teacher gives way and place to the activity of the trainees, his task is to create conditions for their initiative. In such training, students are not passive "learners", but full participants, their experience is no less important than the experience of the teacher, who does not give ready-made knowledge, but encourages students an independent search. The scientific and methodological foundations on which interactive learning is based are: learning through experience and cooperation, taking into account differences in cognition styles, search and research methods, game methods. In a word, the introduction of interactive learning in the educational process in universities will allow students to develop the ability of independent thinking, making smart decision.

The main feature of any innovation is its use in practice and obtaining a positive effect. Realizing the newness and priority of the issue, it should be worked on the formation and education of innovative culture. For an educational institution, it is determined by the following. Firstly, the effectiveness of innovation activity depends on the innovative potential of scientific and educational institutions, and on the activity of inventors. Secondly, taking into account the specifics of the tasks of specialized universities, it is necessary to expand cooperation with scientists from related universities in every possible way. Thirdly, the process of developing a new, introducing innovations, as experience shows, requires systematic work at all stages of training. Usually, it is activated during the preparation of the dissertation research, when the specialist has gained the experience of a large-scale, logical-systemic vision of the issue and its non-standard solution is acquired.

Each period of the society's development sets its own priorities. Personnel training has always been defined as its complex component with special requirements for the educator. Today it is necessary to attract young people to research creativity [1:1-6]. I think everyone agrees with the thesis that this is a complex process that requires managers and mentors, in addition to knowledge, a wide range of qualities from the category of "human dimension", and of course a personal example - "A true scientist-mentor is not the one who fills the cup with knowledge, but the one who lights the torch of knowledge." An important component of improving the effectiveness of the educational process is the educational nature of training. The realization of educational potential at the university is carried out in various directions. Undoubtedly, the basis and priority goal of education at the university is the formation and development of students' qualities and attitudes of a citizen- patriot, professional and highly moral personality.

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